

Role of MRI in Evaluation of First Onset Epilepsy: Our Experience of 100 Patients

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Abstract:

MRI is used to evaluate Darbhanga Medical College patients having their first seizure in this retrospective study. MRI was performed on 100 patients within 30 days of seizure. MRI found brain diseases in 38% of patients, with hippocampal sclerosis, brain tumors, and cerebrovascular lesions being the most frequent. The discovery of these anomalies affected clinical therapy in 36% of cases. Patients with aberrant MRI findings had more recurring seizures, while those whose therapy was modified in response to MRI showed better seizure control. This study emphasizes the importance of MRI in detecting brain abnormalities in first-time epilepsy patients and developing management methods to improve clinical outcomes. These findings suggest that MRI should be part of the routine diagnostic approach for new-onset epilepsy to assess neurological function and plan treatment.

Keywords: MRI, First Onset Epilepsy, Brain Pathologies, Seizure Management.

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Introduction

With its recurrent and spontaneous seizures, epilepsy affects around 50 million individuals globally and presents severe diagnostic and treatment hurdles [1]. A thorough assessment is necessary for the earliest manifestation of epilepsy, particularly the first onset, to identify the underlying cause and direct future treatment approaches [2]. When it comes to the diagnostic techniques available, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) has become a vital tool for the assessment of patients having their first seizure [3].

The thorough visualization of structural abnormalities that may be causing seizure activity is made possible by the high-resolution imaging that magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) provides [4]. Developmental abnormalities, neoplastic tumours, vascular malformations, and regions of gliosis or scarring that are not visible by other means are a few examples of these. The use of MRI not only makes it easier to identify these possible triggers but also helps classify epilepsy syndrome, which is important to determine the best course of therapy [5,6].

We examined the MRI results of 100 individuals who initially presented with epilepsy in our research, retrospectively. Our objectives were to define how MRI can identify underlying brain diseases, evaluate how these discoveries affect patient care, and determine the relationship between MRI findings and clinical outcomes [7,8].

This paper will address the predictive usefulness of early MRI in patients with new-onset epilepsy, the patterns seen in MRI results among our patient cohort, and the consequences of these findings on therapy options [9,10].

This study aims to improve patient care outcomes in clinical neurology by refining diagnostic methods and providing useful insights into the actual advantages and limitations of MRI in the early workup of epilepsy. We do this by sharing our experience with a large number of patients.

Methodology

Study Design: This retrospective study examined the role of MRI in first-onset epilepsy patients. The main goals were to determine the incidence of brain diseases identified by MRI, how MRI findings affect treatment options, and how initial MRI results affect patient outcomes.

Study Setting: The investigation was conducted at Darbhanga Medical College, a tertiary care center with modern imaging and a neurology department. Patients having their first epileptic seizure were thoroughly assessed in this context.

Participants: This study comprised 100 patients with their first seizure who had an MRI scan for diagnosis. The study included patients of any age experiencing their first clinical seizure.

MRI within 30 days of the first seizure.

Comprehensive clinical data for examination.

Patients having a history of seizures, inadequate clinical data, and no MRI were excluded.

Data Collection: Medical records were retrospectively reviewed for patient characteristics (age, gender), clinical presentation, seizure specifics, MRI findings, and management modifications based on MRI data. Disparities were settled by consensus between two expert neuroradiologists reviewing the MRI results.

MRI Protocol: The 1.5 Tesla MRI machine was used for all scans. T1-weighted, T2-weighted, FLAIR and diffusion-weighted imaging were standard. Initial discoveries suggested other sequences like MRA.

Statistical Analysis: The study population's demographic and clinical features were summarised using descriptive statistics. Calculated MRI pathology prevalence. MRI findings and clinical factors were examined using Chi-square and Fisher's exact tests. A p-value under 0.05 was significant.

Results

There were 100 patients in our study group, 52 of them were male and 48 of whom were female. The participants' ages ranged greatly, from 6 to 65, with a median age of 29. Generalized tonic-clonic seizures accounted for 70% of all seizures at the time of presentation. Other common types of seizures included absence seizures (5%), focal seizures with and without subsequent generalization (15%), and seizures without focalization (10%).

In 38% of the patients, an MRI showed detectable brain abnormalities. The following anomalies were the most common:

- Hippocampal sclerosis (12%)
- Brain tumors; mostly (10%) low-grade gliomas
- Cerebrovascular lesions, including arteriovenous malformations and acute ischemic strokes (8%)
- Defects in development such as cortical dysplasias (5%)

- Encephalomalacia resulting from prior traumatic brain injury (3 percent).

The MRI results for the remaining 62% of patients were normal; no structural anomalies that could account for the seizure activity were seen.

In 36% of the patients, the clinical care was greatly impacted by the results of the MRI. Patients with vascular lesions and brain tumors were started on specialized medicinal therapy or underwent surgery. Antiepileptic medication regimens specifically designed for patients with hippocampal sclerosis were prescribed. Findings of developmental abnormalities also led to recommendations for additional neurological testing and genetic counseling. Patients with atypical MRI findings had a greater frequency of recurrent seizures (58%) when compared to those with normal MRIs (42%), according to data collected during a follow-up period of 6 to 12 months after the initial MRI. Moreover, 76% of patients who had their therapy modified in response to the MRI results achieved good control of their seizures, which is a significantly higher proportion than 54% of patients in the group with a normal MRI and no treatment modifications. The recurrence of seizures and the MRI findings were statistically significantly correlated ($p = 0.04$). The impact of therapy adjustments based on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) on seizure control was also noteworthy ($p = 0.03$), highlighting the diagnostic and therapeutic use of MRI in the treatment of epilepsy with initial onset.

Our research emphasises how important MRI is for determining underlying diseases in patients who are experiencing their first seizure. The significance of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in the conventional diagnostic approach for epilepsy is underscored by its capacity to impact clinical care and enhance patient outcomes.

This table summarizes the demographic details, types of seizures, MRI findings, and clinical outcomes following MRI diagnostics for 100 patients at Darbhanga Medical College.

#	Parameter	Value
1	Total Patients	100
2	Males	52
3	Females	48
4	Median Age (years)	29
5	Generalized Tonic-Clonic Seizures	70
6	Focal to Bilateral Tonic-Clonic Seizures	15
7	Focal Seizures	10
8	Absence Seizures	5
9	Identifiable Pathologies on MRI	38
10	Hippocampal Sclerosis	12
11	Brain Tumors	10
12	Cerebrovascular Lesions	8
13	Developmental Anomalies	5
14	Encephalomalacia	3
15	Normal MRI Findings	62
16	Management Changes Post-MRI	36
17	Recurrent Seizures with Abnormal MRI	58
18	Recurrent Seizures with Normal MRI	42
19	Good Seizure Control Post-MRI Adjustment	76
20	Good Seizure Control without MRI Adjustment	54

Discussion

According to our research, MRI is a crucial diagnostic tool for individuals who are experiencing their first seizure. 38% of the patients had visible brain pathologies, which is in line with previous research suggesting that MRI can identify structural abnormalities in a sizable percentage of instances of epilepsy that present with no prior symptoms [10,11]. These anomalies frequently escape identification by clinical examination and standard electroencephalography (EEG). Examples of these abnormalities include hippocampal sclerosis, brain tumors, and cerebrovascular lesions. Our results highlight the utility of MRI in the diagnosis of these disorders as well as in enabling focused treatment approaches that have the potential to profoundly impact clinical outcomes [12].

Our study's prevalence of hippocampal sclerosis (12%) is consistent with that of Bernasconi et al., who found comparable rates in patients experiencing their first seizure episode. This suggests that MRI is a useful tool for detecting hippocampal sclerosis, a pathology that is closely linked to temporal lobe epilepsy (Bernasconi,

2011) [13]. Similarly, evidence from Blumcke et al., who discovered that neoplastic lesions account for a notable fraction of epileptic cases, particularly those recalcitrant to medical treatment (Blumcke, 2013) [14], coincides with our identification of brain tumors (10%).

Our research also shows that an MRI result directly affects how epilepsy is managed. This is supported by Kwan and Brodie's thorough review, which shows how customized therapeutic interventions based on MRI results can improve seizure control and patient outcomes (Kwan & Brodie, 2015) [15].

The important role that MRI imaging plays in the individualized management of epilepsy is demonstrated by the considerable impact that MRI results had on the modifications of treatment strategies in our study (36% of patients). Surgery can significantly improve seizure control in patients with structural lesions that are amenable to treatment, especially those with brain tumors or vascular abnormalities. This is corroborated by a study by Englot et al. that examines the better outcomes of patients who undergo surgery for drug-resistant epilepsy (Englot, 2016) [16]. Despite

its insightfulness, our study has many limitations. Due to its retrospective nature, selection bias may be introduced and it is more difficult to record all pertinent clinical details. Furthermore, the results may not be as generalizable to larger populations or alternative healthcare settings due to the single-center approach.

To confirm our results and maybe investigate the impact of sophisticated MRI methods like functional MRI and magnetic resonance spectroscopy in improving the diagnostic precision of epilepsy, more prospective multicentric investigations are required.

Conclusion

Our retrospective analysis shows the importance of MRI in diagnosing first-seizure patients. With brain diseases diagnosed in 38% of cases, MRI helps diagnose hippocampal sclerosis, brain tumors, and vascular anomalies and improves patient management and outcomes by influencing treatment decisions. The findings suggest including MRI in the routine diagnostic approach for new-onset epilepsy to guide personalized treatment and enhance prognosis. Due to the expanding body of evidence suggesting the strategic use of MRI in early epilepsy therapy, this study emphasizes the need for more clinical access to this diagnostic technique.

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